

A Systematic Review of Research on The Influence of The Media on Body Image

Smita B Thomas¹ & Suphala Kotian²

¹ Research Scholar, College of Social Science & Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0001-9895-6024; E-mail: smitabijuthomas@gmail.com

² Professor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India OrcidID: 0000-0002-5747-4982;

E-mail: suphalakotian@gmail.com

*Corresponding Author contact Number: - +919448723111

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Smartphones and other internet-connected devices have brought us dangerously near to a celebrity's personal life. The intentional portrayal of the glamour industry as just the 'best, most beautiful, and most flawless' hides the enormous sum of money that go into it. An army of personnel to clothe them, apply flawless makeup to conceal defects in every apparent area of their bodies, and a photographer to capture those perfect photos and then edit them to add the extra wow effects. But what we don't see is a large crew caring after their "ideally fit and skinny" body, cooks preparing calorie-counted meals as directed by their high-end celebrity dietician, the costliest celebrity trainer assisting them in burning the precise number of calories and so on. The research was done to understand the existing literature that studies the enormous strain on the human mind to appear flawless thus having body image issues. And also, to determine how social media influencers influence the general public. The researcher wants to instil a feeling of responsibility in celebrities and raise awareness among the general public about the need of focusing on health and quality of life rather than idealising slender bodies.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The research is based on a qualitative review of 5 books, 5 online articles, and 15 research paper references in order to better understand the impact of celebrities on ordinary people.*

Findings/Result: *The findings of this literature review show that media is linked to body image disruption. This is in contrast to previous reviews that focused on a specific aspect of body image. As a result, this literature analysis provides a more nuanced and complete estimate of the strength of the association between social media use and body image disturbance than those previously provided.*

Originality/Value: *- This is the first complete evaluation of the literature in this topic that the authors are aware of. The study reviews the existing literature on influence of media on body image.*

Paper Type: *Review of existing literature*

Keywords: -Body Image, Body dysmorphic disorder, Body Shaming, social media, Media, Body Shape

1. INTRODUCTION:

The majority of us have smart phones and quick internet access, the celebrity world appears alluring and appealing to all. It's just too evident for normal people to try to keep up with their current trends and styles. We don't have to wait for the fortnightly publications to find out what the season's style is. Every day, we are bombarded with the latest fashion trends. These influences, whether intentionally or unintentionally, cause a variety of body image issues, often known as body dysmorphic disorder. We live in a culture that encourages unrealistic expectations because, as the saying goes, "what's seen, sells!" However, if someone is unable to meet these so-called set standards, they may experience sadness, lack of confidence, self-loathing, and anxiety. Due to an inferiority complex or self-doubt, this may cause a person to be socially aloof and shun social gatherings. The glamour business slowly but systematically taught us that fair is beautiful and skinny is fit, and now that the damage has been done to a large extent, they also advise us to "end body shaming." The era when curvaceous actresses were admired gave way to the era when the zero figure became fashionable. The current tendency is to be fit, yet keeping a lean body is essential. Cosmetic operations, silicone implants, Botox, fillers, steroids, hormonal overdoes, crash diets, excessive exercise, vitamins, and other procedures are only the tip of the iceberg to attain this goal. The self-learned idea about how one perceives his or her body is referred to as body image. The minor changes we make in

our daily routine to combat perceived defects in body image can range from healthy changes to going too far and causing more harm than good to our bodies. Physique image issues occur when a person becomes overly critical of his or her own body. It disrupts his bodily and mental equilibrium, or it consumes a lot of energy and time from one's life while being preoccupied with one's appearance. We don't realise how the industry's influence sneaks into us like a gradual poison through our habitual behaviours such as hair colouring, straightening, cosmetics, frequent outfit changes, dieting to death, and so on. Individuals with body image issues gradually withdraw from the world and try to avoid any form of social interaction. The persistent fear that others are looking at him or her and recognising or commenting about his or her defects makes them feel extremely vulnerable. These kinds of incidents cause a lot of anxiety, self-doubt, and a trend that can lead to the person harming himself. It's past time for us to hold these celebrities accountable for their social behaviour. Those who the world watches should be concerned about the lyrics, language, and dance routines they push to the public, which includes a large number of young people who strive to imitate them in any way they can. We also need to provide folks going through a midlife crisis, both men and women, the same amount of attention.

1.1 Definition

Body image refers to a person's perception of himself and how he feels about his own body. In his book 'The Image and Appearance of the Human Body (1935),' Austrian neurologist and psychotherapist Paul Schiller originated the term. Body image literature has focused on two aspects: body perception and body satisfaction. 1.1.2 Body Dimorphic Disorder (BDD) is a mental health problem in which one or more body regions are misperceived. Individuals with BDD believe they have a minor or non-existent flaw in their looks. 1.1.3 Social networking sites, such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter, are online platforms that allow users to produce and share sharp visual and textual information with other people. 1.1.4 The majority of people in their forties and fifties have middle-age crises. It is recognised that maintaining a good body image in society requires attention to how the body appears externally and is regarded in society. Fary M Cachelin and I Diane M Lewis conducted a study on eating attitudes, body dissatisfaction, and body image in 125 middle-aged [50-65yrs] women and senior people. 125 old women (aged 66 and up) were studied to see if there were any differences in eating attitudes, the desire to be thin, and body image between middle-aged and elderly women. The findings suggested that middle-aged women were more concerned about food and had a greater desire to be slender, with an underlying interceptive confusion. Fascinatingly, women in their 60s had body size desires, and their dissatisfaction was similar to that of young women. The fear of ageing was found to be directly linked to disordered eating. The conclusion said that the social and cultural aspects were important.

1.2 Men and Women Disparity In Body Image

On October 11, 2013, the 'Journal of Women and Aging' published an online survey that indicated that only 12.2% of women aged 50 and up were satisfied with their body size. The study came to the conclusion that finding people who have positive feelings about their bodies and treat them with respect and affection is extremely challenging. Another study looked at the relationship between gender and several characteristics that affect body image satisfaction. The findings revealed that women and men sense unhappiness with their bodies in various ways and to different degrees, and that this is largely based on the cultural ideology outlined for women and men. The data also indicated that women's self-perception was more likely to be associated to low self-worth and despair, both of which were linked to body image fulfilment. Individual attitudes about apparent control toward obtaining the so-called "ideal" were investigated in samples.

2. INFLUENCE OF MEDIA WITH BODY IMAGE :

The presence of body image dissatisfaction in adult women and men was determined in a study published in Volume 31 of 'social behaviour and personality: an international journal.' Researchers studied 139 adults' body image dissatisfaction and the factors that contributed to it. They discovered that media influence played a major role in body dissatisfaction in women, and that age, family pressure, and self-worth all contributed to body image dissatisfaction in both men and women. Researchers proposed that because adults' attitudes toward their bodies have an impact on the children around them, studies on body image, dissatisfaction, and related issues should be conducted in adult populations as well. In 2012, a national sample study with a sample size of 11,017 people was undertaken in New Zealand to learn about the impact of social media like Facebook, peer-based media, and transitional media forms. They proposed the following hypothesis: They postulated that middle-aged women were particularly vulnerable because of societal pressure to conform to youthful beauty standards. They looked at the relationship between Facebook use and body satisfaction in women and men of various ages. They utilised a Bayesian regression model to evaluate the curvilinear effects of age, and the findings showed that owning and utilising a Facebook page is associated with lower body satisfaction in both men and women of all ages. A U-

shaped curvilinear relationship was discovered between age and body satisfaction level among female Facebook users; there was a distinct discrepancy in reported body satisfaction between Facebook users and non-users. Young women exhibited lower body satisfaction, according to the findings. Overall, this points to the importance of performing further study on body satisfaction in older groups.

3. METHODOLOGY:

Google scholar, Shodh Ganga, Britannica, National Digital Library of India, Academia, Research Gate, PubMed, and Web of Science were searched in August 2021 for empirical examinations of body image issues influenced by media depiction. Keywords and relevant terminology were used to capture both constructions pertaining to media portrayals of the glamour world and the various components of body image. Body image, Body Dimorphic Disorder, Positive Body Image, Negative Body Image, social media, social network, SNS, Facebook, Instagram, and review were used as search phrases to capture social media. Body image, body, appearance, dissatisfaction, satisfaction, eats, disorder, internalise, fat, thin, and muscular were chosen as search phrases to capture the components of body image. In addition to the current systematic search of journal publications, the reference lists of included articles and pertinent review articles were checked for any new relevant articles that should be included. In October of 2021, a secondary search was undertaken to find any new papers that had been published after the initial search. Books on the topic of body image perceptions were also reviewed in order to gain a better understanding of the theoretical constructs, definitions, and validated and widely accepted assessment tools on body image perceptions. These tools ranged from self-assessment to clinical assessment tools for the diagnosis or treatment of comorbid conditions such as BDD, eating disorders, sleeping disorders, and Bigorexia, among others. Articles found through database searches were initially evaluated based on their titles, then abstracts, and ultimately the complete journal article, in accordance with PRISMA principles. Articles were considered in the initial title screening step if the title suggested that the study was about media use and body image in general. At the abstract screening step, the same procedure was used; both quantitative and qualitative research were included. Finally, the full-text articles of the submitted abstracts were assessed for eligibility; papers were discarded if they lacked an independent measure of media depiction and/or an independent measure of overall or a component of body image. The section below provides a detailed discussion of all inclusion and exclusion criteria.

4. INCLUSION CRITERIA:

Studies have to meet the following inclusion criteria in order to be considered for the analysis. a. An independent measure of media use had to be included in the studies. The term "media use" was used in a broad sense, implying that any part of media use was acceptable. The goal was to standardise a specific body form, fashion style, body measurements, and data. b. A measure of participants' positive or negative body image, or a component of their body image, had to be included in the studies. Measures of overall body contentment or unhappiness were included. (e.g., BISI, BCS tools etc) c. Article written in English.

5. EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

a. Articles not in English b. Articles that are older than last 20 yrs.

6. MEASURES:

The articles were categorised under the following headings. • Body dissatisfaction • Glamour industry depictions • Body Image disturbances • Thin idealisation • Impact of social media on predefined body image • Advertisement industry beauty standards • Celebrity beauty standards • Cosmetic surgeries to fit into beauty standards • Body dysmorphic disorder • Clinical symptoms and treatment of body dysmorphic disorder

7. DISCUSSION:

Only 2% of girls around the world would characterise themselves as beautiful, according to a global survey (Etc off, Orbach, Scott, & D'Agostino, 2004). The literature on the relationship between social media use and body image is considerable, yet the results are inconsistent. Some correlational researches have shown a link between social media use and body image disturbance, while others have discovered a link between social media use and a good body image (e.g., Chae, 2017; Ridgway & Clayton, 2016). According to other studies, there is no link between these two characteristics (e.g., Cohen, Newton-John, & Slater, 2017; Xiaoping, 2017). Despite these inconsistent findings, the idea that the media should be held responsible for the body image culture it promotes is concerning. When studies show that regular social media use is associated to body image problems, it's frequently reported in the news, often in exaggerated and fear-inducing ways (Ch'in, 2018; Thomas, 2018). The idea that social media is "evil" is also evident in the numerous body positivity movements that have sprung up on social

media. The body positivity movement refers to any message communicated through various media with the goal of challenging cultural expectations about appearance, beauty, and bodies while simultaneously encouraging self-acceptance (Cynara-Horta, 2016). This trend has invaded social media platforms due to the recognition of social media and thus the glorified content on social media. Hash tags like "#stopbodyshaming," "#beautybias," "#InMyOwnSkin," and "#allbodiesaregoodbodies," as well as Dove advertising, aim to counter social media's body ideals and urge people to embrace their own bodies. Various topologies have been proposed, but Thompson and van den Berg (2002) give a four-component model that is often used and quoted in the literature (e.g., Grabe & Hyde, 2006; Grabe et al., 2008; Grogan, 2016). The first is the emotive component, which includes how one feels about their body and thus the feelings associated with their body evaluation (e.g., appearance esteem). The cognitive dimension, which includes one's views about their body, is the second (e.g., internalisation of the thin-ideal). Third, there is the behavioural component, which includes acts that are related with one's personal perception of their body (e.g., disordered eating). The fourth dimension is subjective contentment, which measures a person's overall satisfaction with their appearance and body. According to Thompson (2004), failure to consider these different dimensions independently may cause an interpretative difficulty. That is, independent variables may or may not have an impact on various dimensions in the same way (e.g., Walden, Thompson, & Wells, 1997). In fact, Grabe and colleagues' (2008) meta-analysis on the influence of media images in body image issues discovered distinct effect sizes for each dimension. If there is a link between media representation and body image disturbance, a meta-analysis of all relevant reviews will give consensus. It will also provide an assessment of the relationship's strength and assist in identifying relevant moderators. Identifying potential moderators may be a particularly important contribution since, as alluded to earlier, this relationship is probably going to vary for various people (i.e., women, those that identify as Caucasian), differing types of social media use (e.g., appearance-focused use), and for the various dimensions of body image. As this is often a growing field of research, the present findings will help to shape future research.

8. LIMITATIONS:

While this literature review fills a void in the body image literature, it is not without flaws. Only cross-sectional studies are included in the analysis. It will be difficult to say whether an individual's pre-existing reasons for body image disturbances cause them to look up to the glamour world or whether the glamour world causes the body image problems. Cross-sectional studies cannot take implicit third factors into consideration when estimating a connection. As a result, it's likely that these figures are inflated or deflated as a result of a third variable that can explain both social media use and body image problems. Tone-regard could be an unspoken third variable. Both social media use and body image have been connected to tone of voice. There was no standardised tool or investigation available to determine if celebrities have a positive or negative impact on individuals. As a result, the experimenter had to rely on evidence.

9. PUBLICATION BIAS :

Studies with substantial findings are more likely to be published than studies with null or insignificant results; this phenomenon is known as publication bias. As a consequence, summary Due to the overrepresentation of significant findings in the literature, effect sizes obtained in the studies may be appreciatively disposed.

10. CONCLUSION :

To summarise, the findings of this literature review show that media is linked to body image disruption. Despite the flaws mentioned, there are numerous positive aspects to this review. This is the first complete evaluation of the literature in this topic that the authors are aware of. This is in contrast to previous reviews that focused on a specific aspect of body image. As a result, this literature analysis provides a more nuanced and complete estimate of the strength of the association between social media use and body image disturbance than those previously provided. The degree of this effect was not as significant as previously predicted based on previous research and popular opinion, suggesting that general social media use may not be as risky as previously predicted for drug addicts. However, it may be especially risky for certain drug addicts (e.g., young addicts) who engage in certain behaviours (i.e., engaging in appearance concentrated social media use). Examining the relationships between variables such as social media influence on body image and tone-of-voice would be an exciting and essential new topic to investigate. What body image issues are related with youngish social media addicts who engage in appearance-focused use, for example? A meta-analysis of only research examining appearance-focused social media use would be one method to investigate this. While several studies have looked into this specific form of social media use, more research is needed before a sufficiently powered meta-analysis can be conducted. This is a promising new option, as the data might be used to build treatments aimed at media figures to encourage them to take a more socially responsible approach to body image. Furthermore, because social networking is still a relatively new

technology, we cannot be certain of the long-term effects it may have on drug addicts. Finally, the authors want to stress that this is an association relationship; consequently, more experimental research is needed to define the implicit counterproductive relationship between body image difficulties and the influence of the glamour world. For easy reference, a summary of the literature evaluated, which includes 5 books, 5 online articles, and 15 research paper references, is presented in a tabular format below.

Books

SN O	BOOK	REFERENCE	CONTENT
1	Understanding Body Dysmorphic Disorder	Phillips, K. (2009). <i>Understanding Body Dysmorphic Disorder</i> . Oxford University Press, USA.	Dr. Katharine A. Phillips created a thorough manual for patients and their physicians in <i>The Broken Mirror</i> , the first and most definitive book on BDD, based on years of clinical experience, scientific research, and professional evaluations of over 1,000 patients. The world's foremost authority on BDD now offers this brief and updated manual to patients, their friends, and their families in <i>Understanding Body Dysmorphic Disorder: An Essential Guide</i> . BDD affects up to 2% of the population, or almost five million people, and causes patients to become obsessed with perceived imperfections in their looks. Dr. Phillips guides readers through the basics of the disorder and through the many treatment options that work and don't work. With <i>Understanding Body Dysmorphic Disorder: An Essential Guide</i> , sufferers will find both helpful advice and much needed reassurance in a compact, down-to-earth indispensable book.
2	Exacting beauty: Theory, assessment, and treatment of body image disturbance.	Thompson, J., Heinberg, L., Altabe, M., & Tantleff-Dunn, S. (1999). <i>Exacting beauty: Theory, assessment, and treatment of body image disturbance</i> . https://doi.org/10.1037/10312-000	Kevin Thompson and his colleagues cover a wide range of body image issues, from reconstructive surgery to eating disorders. Even the most seasoned scholars in the field will find the book useful because it is packed with data, information about assessment techniques, and a full treatment of practically all important theoretical viewpoints on the development of body image and their implications for therapy and prevention. At the same time, the writers' decision to incorporate several personal tales makes the book approachable to individuals who are new to the area and want to learn more about these occurrences.
3	Diagnostic and Statistical	American Psychiatric Association.	Kevin Thompson and his colleagues cover a wide range of body image

	Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5®)	(2013). Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5®) (5th ed., pp. 234-247).	issues, from reconstructive surgery to eating disorders. Even the most seasoned scholars in the field will find the book useful because it is packed with data, information about assessment techniques, and a full treatment of practically all important theoretical viewpoints on the development of body image and their implications for therapy and prevention. At the same time, the writers' decision to incorporate several personal tales makes the book approachable to individuals who are new to the area and want to learn more about these occurrences.
4	Body Image	Grogan, S. Body image (3rd ed.). Taylor & Francis.	<p>Body Image brings together data from the domains of psychology, sociology, clothes, and gender studies to present a thorough overview of study on body image in men, women, and children.</p> <p>This edition has been completely changed and updated to reflect substantial advances in body image research since the last edition, as well as important cultural shifts in how men's and women's bodies are perceived. Data from interviews and focus groups with men, women, and children who have discussed their experiences with body image and dissatisfaction are also included, resulting in a thorough picture of how men and women construct and interpret their bodies in the twenty-first century.</p> <p>This book will be beneficial to students and academics, as well as practitioners, who are interested in body image and how to reduce body dissatisfaction. It is the only single-authored work to present a complete picture of body image research, concentrating on men, women, and children.</p>
5	In our Prime: - The Invention of middle age	Cohen, P. (2012). In our prime: The invention of middle age (pp. Pg 7,11).	As per Ms. Cohen, in this book marketers in the cosmetics, advertising, and entertainment industries have been vying for a piece of the lucrative middle-aged image reversal pie. They're attempting to make middle-aged people appear "thinner, smoother, sexier, wealthier, happier, and hipper." In reality, the middle-feeling has become more powerful, lively, and appealing as a result of this.

			However, the book also examines the real self, which is under to even more pressure to appear a specific way.
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WEBSITES

SN O	Website and Article	REFERENCE	CONTENT
1	Breakbingeeating.com . The Ultimate List of Body Image Statistics in 2021	Linardon, D. (2021). <i>2021 Body Image Statistics: 40 Shocking Body Image Facts</i> . BreakBinge Eating. Retrieved 26 November 2021	Summarises key statistics on body image in men and women for the year 2021 including children, teenagers and adults of both the genders.
2	Pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov.com Body dysmorphic disorder	Body dysmorphic disorder. (2010), <i>12</i> (2), 221-232.	The research findings on BDD, including its occurrence, signs and symptoms, prognosis, comorbidity, mental status, and suicidality, are summarised in this paper. Recent research on neurological substrates and cognitive processing is also reviewed. Finally, the essay addresses the treatment options for BDD that appear to be helpful, with a focus on selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors and cognitive behavioural therapy.
3	Pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov.com Pharmacotherapy and psychotherapy for body dysmorphic disorder	Ipsier, J., Sander, C., & Stein, D. (2009). Pharmacotherapy and psychotherapy for body dysmorphic disorder. <i>Cochrane Database Of Systematic Reviews</i> . 2009;01-21	Serotonin reuptake inhibitors and Cognitive behavioural therapy may be helpful in treating people with BDD, according to this paper. Future controlled investigations in additional samples utilising other selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, as well as a variety of psychological therapy, different techniques and modalities (alone or in combination), were also emphasised in the study to enhance the current results.
4	Academia.edu.com Validation of a French measure of body comparison: The Physical Appearance Comparison Scale.	Dany, L. (2021). Validation of a French measure of body comparison: The Physical Appearance Comparison Scale. <i>Academia.edu</i> . Repéré 11 May 2021, à https://www.academia.edu/1850223/Validati	The validity of the French version of the Physical Appearance Comparison Scale was investigated (PACS; Thompson, Heinberg, & Tantleff, 1991). 297 university students, the majority of whom are female, between the ages of 18 and 20, attended two French universities. The acquired results were consistent with the original version, with strong

		on_of_a_French_measure_of_body_comparison The Physical Appearance Comparison Scale	internal consistency and test-retest repeatability. Body image self-esteem, social physique anxiety, body size satisfaction, self-weighting, body size estimation, and depression were all substantially connected with the French PACS scores. This metric contributed to a better understanding of the process of body dissatisfaction and how it affects psychological suffering.
5	King University Online. The link between social media and body image.	<i>Link Between Social Media & Body Image King University Online</i> . King University Online. (2021). Retrieved 26 November 2021, from https://online.king.edu/news/social-media-and-body-image/ .	The essay emphasised how social media is influencing people's perceptions of beauty. For better or worse, we are continually ingesting images uploaded online. As a result, social media and body image are now inextricably connected. Social media has a positive or bad impact on our perceptions, and it's critical that we recognise these effects in order to reduce their negative impact on our mental health.

RESEARCH ARTICLES

1	Body dysmorphic disorder: recognizing and treating imagined ugliness	Phillips, K. (2021). <i>Body dysmorphic disorder: recognizing and treating imagined ugliness</i> . PubMed Central (PMC). Retrieved 29 November 2021, from https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1414653/ .	This page discusses the main evidence-based research that have been conducted on the available therapy methods for BDD patients. Although understanding of BDD is rapidly expanding, the author believes that more study is needed on all facets of the disorder, including treatment trials, epidemiology studies, and investigations into its cross-cultural traits and causation.
2	Beauty and Thinness Messages in Children's Media: A Content Analysis	HERBOZO, S., TANTLEFF-DUNN, S., GOKEE-LAROSE, J., & THOMPSON, J. (2004). Beauty and Thinness Messages in Children's Media: A Content Analysis. <i>Eating Disorders</i> , 12(1), 21-34.	According to research, young toddlers are developing body image concerns, such as a desire for thinness and a desire to avoid obesity. A few research on youngsters looked into how media influences their body preferences and stereotypes. A content analysis was done to evaluate the body image-related messages contained in popular children's movies and books in order to better comprehend this. Cinderella and The Little Mermaid had the most body

			<p>image-related messages out of all the videos studied, according to the findings. Indian in the Cupboard and ET were the videos with the fewest body image-related messages. Rapunzel had the most body image-related messaging out of all of the books examined. Ginger and The Stinky Cheese Man were the only books that didn't include any messages about body image. This showed a clear link between what children's media portrays and how it affects them.</p>
3	The Good, the Bad, and the Beautiful	<p>Northup, T., & Liebler, C. (2010). The Good, the Bad, and the Beautiful. <i>Journal Of Children And Media</i>, 4(3), 265-282.</p>	<p>This study focused on the beauty ideal messages sent by live-action television shows aimed at young girls. Nine Disney and Nickelodeon shows were subjected to a detailed content review. The results imply that the skinny, white beauty ideal seen in adult media is also seen in programmes aimed at a younger audience. The idea that "beauty and thinness is excellent" is also reinforced through the major characters' vocal messaging. In the context of Social Comparison Theory, the findings and implications were addressed.</p>
4	Thin is "in" and stout is "out": What animated cartoons tell viewers about body weight	<p>Klein, H., & Shiffman, K. (2005). Thin is "in" and stout is "out": What animated cartoons tell viewers about body weight. <i>Eating And Weight Disorders - Studies On Anorexia, Bulimia And Obesity</i>, 10(2), 107-116.</p>	<p>The following concerns are investigated in this study:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> In animated cartoons, how prevalent is weight-related content? Has the frequency of this incidence changed over time? Which "categories" of physical appearance are related with being slimmer or heavier than average? <p>The proportion of both underweight and overweight characters has changed considerably over the last several decades, according to the findings. The nature of these interactions is curvilinear. In recent years, there has been a large increase in the proportion of all cartoons with slim characters and a parallel decrease in the prevalence of overweight characters. Many variables were discovered to have a distinct discrimination. For example, big, heavy characters were frequently shown as greedy, stupid, or cruel,</p>

			<p>whereas slender, attractive, fair ones were consistently depicted as well-off, educated, pro-social, and smart. Characters that were extremely skinny and unkempt were frequently shown as being from a lower socioeconomic status. As a result, the cartoons plainly convey both positive and negative signals about being skinny and overweight.</p>
5	<p>Does Barbie make girls want to be thin? The effect of experimental exposure to images of dolls on the body image of 5- to 8-year-old girls</p>	<p>Dittmar, H., Halliwell, E., & Ivey, S. (2006). Does Barbie make girls want to be thin? The effect of experimental exposure to images of dolls on the body image of 5- to 8-year-old girls. <i>Developmental Psychology</i>, 42(2), 283-292.</p>	<p>The Barbie doll was investigated in this study as a probable source of body dissatisfaction in young girls. A total of 162 girls between the ages of 5 and 8 were given photographs of Barbie dolls, Emme dolls (US size 16), or no dolls (baseline control) before completing a body image assessment. Barbie-exposed girls had poorer self-esteem and a stronger desire for a slimmer body shape than the other control groups. The older girls, on the other hand, did not seem to be affected by the Barbie doll. These findings suggest that, even if dolls do not serve as aspirational role models for older girls, early exposure to dolls who personify an excessively slim body ideal may harm a girl's body image, increasing the risk of disordered eating and weight cycling.</p>
6	<p>Reading magazine articles about dieting and associated weight control behaviours among adolescents</p>	<p>Utter, J., Neumarksztaier, D., Wall, M., & Story, M. (2003). Reading magazine articles about dieting and associated weight control behaviours among adolescents. <i>Journal Of Adolescent Health</i>, 32(1), 78-82.</p>	<p>The goal of this study was to look at the socio-demographic features of young people who read articles about dieting and weight loss, as well as the link between reading these articles and psychosocial well-being and weight-control behaviour. Dieting-related exposure was linked to indices of psychosocial distress and inappropriate dieting; media consumption interventions should target all youth, regardless of ethnic or social background.</p>
7	<p>Social comparisons on social media: The impact of Facebook on young women's body image concerns and mood</p>	<p>Fardouly, J., Diedrichs, P., Vartanian, L., & Halliwell, E. (2015). Social comparisons on social media: The impact of Facebook</p>	<p>The purpose of this study was to see how Facebook affects women's mood and body image. And to see if the urge to compare appearances moderates any of these effects. These effects may differ from those of a fashion magazine published online. There were 122</p>

		on young women's body image concerns and mood. <i>Body Image</i> , 13, 38-45.	female participants in the study. They were given 10 minutes to browse their Facebook account, a magazine website, or an appearance-neutral control website before being asked to complete the body dissatisfaction, mood, and appearance discrepancies questionnaires (weight-related, and face, hair, and skin-related). They also completed a trait assessment of the desire to compare appearances. The people who spent time on Facebook were in a more negative mood than those who spent time on the control websites, according to the findings. Furthermore, women with a high inclination to compare their appearance to others reported higher physical appearance disparities after exposure to Facebook than after exposure to the control website. More research, is needed to understand the negative impact of FB according to the author.
8	Body Image Concern Inventory (BICI) for Identifying Patients with BDD Seeking Rhinoplasty: Using a Persian (Farsi) Version.	Ghadakzadeh, S., Ghazipour, A., Khajeddin, N., Karimian, N., & Borhani, M. (2011). <i>Body Image Concern Inventory (BICI) for Identifying Patients with BDD Seeking Rhinoplasty: Using a Persian (Farsi) Version</i> . <i>Aesthetic Plastic Surgery</i> , 35(6), 989-994.	The findings of this study show that patients seeking rhinoplasty have a high rate of BDD (12.2%). According to the author, the BICI scale was utilised for the first time in a rhinoplasty scenario to identify BDD patients; it was also the first time that receiver operating characteristic analysis was employed to calculate and analyse BICI data. According to the findings, rhinoplasty surgeons might rely on BICI scores to identify people with suspected BDD among their patients with no or one minor problem.
9	Validation of the Chinese Version of the Body Image Concern Inventory	Wang, K., Yu, X., Yu, C., Liu, Y., Chu, M., & Zhang, R. et al. (2020). <i>Validation of the Chinese Version of the Body Image Concern Inventory. Evaluation & The Health Professions</i> .	The purpose of the research was to look at the psychometric qualities of a brand new Chinese BICI. In Study 1, 1,231 Chinese young adults were given the Chinese version of BICI, along with 47 female eating problem patients and 56 matched controls (ED; Study 2) The findings revealed that the Chinese version of the BICI tool was a valid and reliable instrument that could be utilised in a variety of situations and ethnic groups.
10	The Struggle Between the Real	Nagar, I., & Virk, R. (2017). <i>The Struggle</i>	The article focuses on how the media has evolved into a powerful weapon for

	and Ideal: Impact of Acute Media Exposure on Body Image of Young Indian Women	Between the Real and Ideal. SAGE Open, 7(1),	defining what a woman's body "should, ought, and must" be. Real women are finding depictions of perfect women to be increasingly unreachable as a result of the "thinning" of beauty ideals in the media. The influence of acute media images on a sample of 60 young adult Indian women was investigated in this exploratory study. Half of the participants were shown thin-ideal media images, while the other half were shown control images, in a two (intervention group) two (time) mixed-group design. Body image dissatisfaction, thin-ideal internalisation, and self-esteem were all assessed in the subjects. As a result of exposure to thin-ideal media representations, the study found an increase in thin-ideal internalisation and body dissatisfaction, as well as a decrease in self-esteem scores. The findings revealed that when young urban Indian women were exposed to thin-ideal images, they had body image issues. The findings were similar to those of a previous study conducted in Europe and North America.
11	Body dysmorphic disorder	S Bjornsson, A., R Didie, E., & A Phillips, K. (2010). Body dysmorphic disorder. <i>Obsessive-Compulsive Spectrum Disorders</i> , 12(2), 221-232.	The article emphasis on BDD as a compulsive-obsessive disorder complaint, based on its similarities to compulsive-obsessive disorders. This review gives us an overview of BDD research findings, including epidemiology, clinical characteristics, illness course, comorbidities, psychosocial functioning, and suicidality. The authors also provide a concise overview of recent research on neural substrates and cognitive processes. They also discuss treatment options for BDD that appear to be helpful, with a focus on serotonin reuptake inhibitors and cognitive-behavioral therapy.
12	Clinical features of body dysmorphic disorder in adolescents and adults	Phillips, K., Didie, E., Menard, W., Pagano, M., Fay, C., & Weisberg, R. (2006). Clinical features of body dysmorphic disorder	This study was done on two hundred individualities with BDD (36 adolescents; 164 grown-ups) using canvasser-administered and tone-report measures. The findings revealed that adolescents were concerned about a variety of characteristics of their

		in adolescents and adults. <i>Psychiatry Research</i> , 141(3), 305-314.	appearance, the most prominent of which were their complexion, hair, and stomach. 94.3 adolescents reported moderate to severe or intense torment as a result of BDD, 80.6 had suicide thoughts, and 44.4 attempted self-murder. Adolescents had high absence rates in school, in employment, and in other areas of sickie-social functioning. Many factors were similar between adolescents and adults, but adolescents reported much more delusional body dysmorphic complaint beliefs, torture, functional impairment, and a higher prevalence of self-murder attempts.
13	Clinical and subclinical body dysmorphic disorder	Altamura, C., Paluello, M., Mundo, E., Medda, S., & Mannu, P. (2001). Clinical and subclinical body dysmorphic disorder. <i>European Archives Of Psychiatry And Clinical Neuroscience</i> , 251(3), 105-108.	The purpose of this study was to determine the demographic and clinical parameters of Body Dysmorphic Complaint and subclinical BDD in 487 samples collected from sanatoriums. As a result, the samples were separated into three sub-samples. 1) BDD, 2) BDD with subclinical symptoms, and 3) a control group. Between the BDD and sub-clinical BDD populations, the key demographic and clinical factors were addressed and compared. According to the findings, the frequency of BDD was 6.3 and that of subclinical BDD was 18.4, respectively. The most common comorbid diagnosis was compulsive-obsessive disorder (OCD). The severity of symptoms was found to have advanced in manish BDD patients, but no gender-related differences were seen in the subclinical BDD group. Suicidal thoughts were observed in 12.1 percent of subclinical BDD cases and 49.7% of BDD cases. The findings suggest that BDD and subclinical BDD are both part of the OCD diapason, and that long-term follow-up research on the course and symptoms are needed.
14	Demographic Characteristics, Phenomenology, Comorbidity, and Family History in 200 Individuals with Body Dysmorphic Disorder	Phillips, K., Menard, W., Fay, C., & Weisberg, R. (2005). Demographic Characteristics, Phenomenology, Comorbidity, and Family History in 200 Individuals with	In this study, the writers looked at the characteristics of body dysmorphic complaint. The researchers contrasted the results of psychiatrically treated and naked people. The author discussed the symptoms and prevalence of body dysmorphic disorder. They seem to have a lot more in common than the distinctions between the dressed and

		Body Dysmorphic Disorder. <i>Psychosomatics</i> , 46(4), 317-325.	nude figures. The treated patients, on the other hand, showed a higher level of intelligence.
15	Comorbidity of body dysmorphic disorder and eating disorders: Severity of psychopathology and body image disturbance	S. Ruffolo, J., Phillips, K., Menard, W., Fay, C., & Weisberg, R. (2006). Comorbidity of body dysmorphic disorder and eating disorders: Severity of psychopathology and body image disturbance. <i>International Journal Of Eating Disorders</i> , 39(1), 11-19. https://doi.org/10.1002/eat.20219	The current study looked at the comorbidity and clinical characteristics of eating disorders in 200 people who had body dysmorphic complaints (BDD). Individuals with BDD are more likely to develop eating disorders. Subjects with BDD and a comorbid eating disorder had less body image disturbance and had had more cerebral treatment than those who did not have a comorbid eating disorder. These findings have significant implications for the diagnosis and management of these comorbid body image disorders.

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